

⟨H/RADIOSA⟩: Recommended Approaches for the Development of Interoperable Open Semantic Artefacts in the Heritage Domain

Erica Scarpa*

Riccardo Valente*

Irene Rossi*

*ISPC - CNR

Introduction	3
Why It Matters	3
Authors	3
How to Cite	3
Actions	4
#1 - Be FAIR (Enough)	4
What Are FAIR Principles?	4
Assessing FAIRness	5
Key Recommendations	5
#2 - Use Semantic Versioning	7
What Is Semantic Versioning?	7
Why It Matters for Heritage Semantic Artefacts	7
Changelogs and Transparency	7
Practical Example	8
Recommendations	8
#3 - Set Responsiveness Expectations	8
Definition	8
List of the Statuses	8
Usage	9
Recommendations	9
#4 - Documentation	9
Documentation issues	9
Proposed Solutions and Best Practices	10
Acknowledgements	11

Introduction

⟨H/RADIOSA⟩ is an initiative that provides actionable **guidelines** and **best practices** for the development of Semantic Artefacts in the Heritage field.¹ It aims to support both domain experts and non-specialists in creating and using high-quality, interoperable resources that comply with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and Linked Data principles. Inspired by the **OBO Foundry**—a community of biological and biomedical experts dedicated to harmonizing domain ontologies and promoting good practices—RADIOSA seeks to address similar needs within the Heritage sector.

Why It Matters

Heritage Semantic Artefacts are often created in **isolation** and exhibit **uneven quality standards**, with many lacking long-term **maintenance** or basic features (such as dereferenceable URIs). Fragmentation makes it difficult for Heritage professionals to **keep pace** with the ever-growing array of initiatives, networks, and outputs emerging in and outside the field, as well as with the increasing demand for interoperable and sustainable digital products—an essential element of the **data-driven science** agenda promoted by recent European programmes such as the **European Open Science Cloud** (EOSC).

The H-SeTIS survey² highlighted the **urgency** of addressing this gap. In response, ⟨H/RADIOSA⟩ is taking the first **concrete steps**. By translating these critical issues into actionable recommendations, ⟨H/RADIOSA⟩ invites researchers and end-users alike to adopt best practices and accelerate the creation of high-quality, standards-compliant Semantic Artefacts. This project leverages data collected through our broader initiative portfolio to offer tools that mitigate fragmentation and help Heritage professionals stay abreast of emerging trends in Semantic Artefact development.

Authors

The ⟨H/RADIOSA⟩ initiative is currently led by Erica Scarpa (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6250-304X>), Riccardo Valente (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8620-0879>), and Irene Rossi (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5820-8256>). If you would like to contribute, share suggestions, or provide feedback, please **open an issue** in the GitLab repository.

How to Cite

You can cite the paper we wrote to promote the initiative:

Scarpa, E., Valente, R., & Rossi, I. (2025). H/RADIOSA: Recommended Approaches for the Development of Interoperable Open Semantic Artefacts in the Heritage Domain. *DH2025 - Digital Heritage International Congress 2025*. <https://doi.org/10.2312/dh.20253041>

or this PDF version of the website.

¹Semantic Artefacts (SAs) comprise ontologies, thesauri, metadata standards, and any resources that sit at the crossroads of these categories. The term Heritage Semantic Artefact (HSA) is used here to denote those SAs that are specifically developed for the Heritage domain.

²On the results of our survey and the description of H-SeTIS, see Scarpa and Valente (2024), “A Resource Hub for Interoperability and Data Integration in Heritage Research: The H-SeTIS Database”, *Archeologia e Calcolatori* 35, 543–62, ([10.19282/ac.35.1.2024.32](https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.35.1.2024.32)), and Scarpa, Valente, and Rossi (2025), “Modeling an Ontology for Heritage Science: Challenges and Key Strategies.” in *Proceedings Del XIV Convegno Annuale AIUCD2025* ([10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8380](https://doi.org/10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8380)).

Actions

Please use [issue tracker](#) to ask further clarification, make suggestions, or new principles you would like to suggest.

#1 - Be FAIR (Enough)

Originally published in 2016, the FAIR principles were conceived for research data management.³ On a general level, they provide the right paradigm for SAs⁴ development because they directly address long-standing challenges. They overcome barriers to discovery and reuse by replacing imprecise metadata and fragmented practices with a structured approach that supports both humans and machines. By making SAs easier to locate and apply, FAIR guidelines reduce development costs and efforts while enhancing the quality of semantic resources. They also bring consistency and clarity to metadata descriptions across platforms and communities, addressing the problem of scattered and inconsistently described artifacts. Beyond technical efficiency, FAIR principles strengthen scientific progress by enabling greater interoperability and data reuse across disciplines, aligning with initiatives like the [Research Data Alliance](#) that emphasize barrier-free data sharing. In doing so, FAIR principles ensure that SAs remain useful, interoperable, and sustainable over time.

Read on below for a deeper look at FAIR data and the tools that support it. RADIOSA encourages the adoption of FAIR (Enough) practices while also highlighting the limitations and potential pitfalls that arise when applying FAIR guidelines in the Heritage sector.

What Are FAIR Principles?

The FAIR guidelines or principles define four key characteristics for digital research data:

- **Findability** – Data should be easy to discover, with persistent identifiers and rich metadata.
- **Accessibility** – Data must be retrievable by standardized protocols and remain available over time.
- **Interoperability** – Data should use shared vocabularies and formats, enabling seamless integration.
- **Reusability** – Data must carry clear licenses, provenance, and metadata that support reuse.

Since the FAIR principles were introduced in 2016, the concept of *FAIRness* has grown beyond data management to encompass a wide range of research outputs—including software and tools. This expansion has driven the creation of new guidelines and the assessment of methods that enable FAIR compliance even before data is produced. In this context, the outcomes of the [FAIRsFAIR](#) project are highly relevant for developers of Heritage Semantic Artefacts (HSAs), as the project has made significant strides in establishing best practices for the development of SAs.

The [H-SeTIS survey](#) revealed that HSAs often fail to meet basic FAIR requirements.⁵ Dissemination is frequently limited to ad hoc methods, such as single RDF/Turtle files or static web pages, and minimal or missing metadata hinders both evaluation and reuse. Licensing practices are often inconsistent, further complicating accessibility and compliance. As a result, even when HSAs exist online, they are difficult to discover, assess, or reuse effectively.

Skeptics might argue that by privileging standardization, reuse, and discoverability, the FAIR principles risk flattening the richness, ambiguity, and difference in interpretations that characterize Heritage data. FAIR is inherently **machine-oriented**, which can conflict with the interpretive and narrative-driven nature of Heritage.

³ Wilkinson, M. D., et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

⁴ Semantic artefacts (SAs) comprise ontologies, thesauri, metadata standards, and any resources that sit at the crossroads of these categories. The term Heritage Semantic Artefact (HSA) is used here to denote those SAs that are specifically developed for the Heritage domain.

⁵ On the results of our survey and the description of H-SeTIS, see Scarpa and Valente (2024), “A Resource Hub for Interoperability and Data Integration in Heritage Research: The H-SeTIS Database”, *Archeologia e Calcolatori* 35, 543–62, ([10.19282/ac.35.1.2024.32](#)), and Scarpa, Valente, and Rossi (2025), “Modeling an Ontology for Heritage Science: Challenges and Key Strategies.” in *Proceedings Del XIV Convegno Annuale AIUCD2025* ([10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8380](#)).

Moreover, FAIR implementation is **not cost-free**: ensuring persistent identifiers, maintaining repositories, providing rich metadata, and securing long-term governance demand stable funding and technical expertise. In practice, maintaining persistent URIs and ensuring resource findability remain particularly challenging in the Heritage domain, as highlighted by the H-SeTIS results. FAIRness, however, is better understood as a spectrum rather than a binary condition, with different levels of compliance achievable depending on context, resources, and community priorities.

Assessing FAIRness

Regardless of whether a SA was created before or after the introduction of the FAIR guidelines, its level of compliance can be evaluated using a range of tools and initiatives that support FAIR assessment and implementation:

- **FOOPS!** (Ontology Pitfall Scanner for FAIR) – evaluates FAIR compliance of ontologies.
- **O'FAIRe**, an open source FAIRness assessment method and tool for SAs.
- FAIR-IMPACT project – provides methodologies for **integrating FAIR solutions** into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as well as **implementation & adoption stories** illustrating good practices to support the implementation of the FAIR principles.

Key Recommendations

Use a FAIR-by-design methodology

A central FAIRsFAIR recommendation is to adopt **FAIR-by-design methodologies** when developing SAs.⁶ When building new HSAs, the best practice is to embed FAIR principles from the outset, rather than adding them retroactively later. One such methodology is **Linked Open Terms (LOT)**.⁷

The LOT methodology proposes a lightweight, iterative workflow that includes Ontological Requirements Specification, Ontology Implementation, Ontology Publication, and Ontology Maintenance. Central to LOT is the reuse of existing terms from published vocabularies, consistent with Linked Data principles, and the publication of ontologies in both human- and machine-readable forms accessible via their URIs. Its iterative, sprint-based workflow integrates smoothly with agile development, enabling rapid progress and frequent releases. By addressing shortcomings in traditional methodologies—such as limited attention to publication and web-based reuse—LOT provides a modern framework that ensures ontologies are not only developed efficiently but also openly available and interoperable from the start.

In the FAIRsFAIR project, a FAIR-by-design approach based on LOT was created: **LOT4FAIR**. LOT4FAIR guarantees that SAs are inherently FAIR, promotes cross-disciplinary semantic interoperability, and enables the construction of FAIR Scientific Knowledge Graphs. It extends LOT with an iterative workflow that aligns with **agile software development practices** (e.g., sprints and iterations). The method emphasizes both reusing existing terms and publishing new ontologies that follow Linked Data principles.⁸ LOT4FAIR incorporates developer experience, best practices, guidelines, and existing ontology-creation tools. It identifies gaps in current guidelines and proposes recommendations to ensure FAIRness at every stage of development.

Implement Identifiers Efficiently

A **Globally Unique, Persistent, Resolvable Identifier** (GUPRI) is an identifier that guarantees uniqueness (being distinct across all systems), persistence (remaining valid over time), and resolvability (being accessible via standard protocols such as HTTP). The use of GUPRIs is recommended for SAs, their contents (including terms, concepts, classes, and relations), as well as their versions. Nevertheless, as illustrated below, the adoption of GUPRIs is not without cost: for smaller heritage institutions, this practice can be administratively

⁶ Jonquet, C., & Grau, N. (2025). D4.2—FAIR Semantic Artefact Lifecycle from Engineering, to Sharing. Zenodo. zenodo.org/records/14643279.

⁷ <https://lot.linkeddata.es/>. See also Poveda-Villalón, M., Fernández-Izquierdo, A., Fernández-López, M., & García-Castro, R. (2022). LOT: An Industrial Oriented Ontology Engineering Framework. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 111, 1–22. [10.1016/j.engappai.2022.104755](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2022.104755).

⁸ Linked Data outlines principles for publishing structured, machine-readable data on the Web in a way that enables it to be interconnected. If the data is compliant with open standards, then you have **Linked Open Data** (LOD).

burdensome, often requiring the minting of hundreds of URIs for only marginal benefit.

The use of URI-based identifiers (e.g., in accordance with [OBO Foundry conventions](#)) and versioned URIs can be supported through services such as [purl.org](#) or [w3id](#). These services enable the creation of persistent URIs that redirect to current resource locations, with w3id additionally offering more granular control over redirection, including the management of different serializations for versioning purposes.

[Digital Object Identifiers](#) (DOIs) represent an additional option for ensuring persistence; however, unlike other solutions, they are not freely available. Whereas w3id relies on GitHub-based workflows, DOI and other PID systems require structured governance mechanisms. It must also be acknowledged that reliance on external PID providers entails certain risks, as policies, funding models, or even the providers themselves may change or disappear (see also below, subsection “Build TRUST to be FAIR”).

Overall, GUPRIs, PIDs, and URIs are fundamental for the creation, dissemination, and FAIRification of SAs. These identifiers are critical enablers of the FAIR principles—ensuring that SAs are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Nonetheless, identifiers alone are insufficient to guarantee FAIRness: while they support Findability and Accessibility, true Interoperability and Reusability depend on the availability of rich metadata, appropriate licensing, and adherence to community conventions.

"Be FAIR and CARE": The Case of Indigenous Data

Some scholars argue that the CARE Principles⁹—Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, and Ethics—offer a path “beyond FAIR” for Indigenous or Heritage contexts. Although a universally accepted definition of “Indigenous peoples” remains elusive, they are generally understood to be communities that possess a long historical continuity with and a deep connection to the land and its natural features. Their socio-economic and political structures, languages, and cultures are distinct from the majority society, and they often hold conservative cultural, social, and religious beliefs. A complementary objective for data stewards and other users of Indigenous data is to “Be FAIR and CARE.” This dual approach seeks to enhance machine actionability (FAIR) while simultaneously safeguarding the unique characteristics, purposes, and rights of specific peoples within data governance.

The CARE Principles from the [Global Indigenous Data Alliance](#) (GIDA) introduce a people- and purpose-oriented perspective that is essential for the development of HSAs, particularly when dealing with Indigenous data or Cultural Heritage. They address the tension that Indigenous communities experience between safeguarding their rights and interests in data—including traditional knowledge—and supporting open-data initiatives. Consequently, applying the CARE Principles in addition to the FAIR Principles in HSA development means designing artefacts that do not exclude Indigenous knowledge systems, thereby moving beyond the worldviews of the societies that originally shaped the mainstream knowledge framework. This requires that the terms, concepts, relationships, and even constraints embedded within semantic artefacts be culturally appropriate and meaningful to the Indigenous communities they describe. Tools such as the [Traditional Knowledge \(TK\) Labels](#) demonstrate how extra-legal digital mechanisms can restore Indigenous cultural authority and governance over Indigenous data and collections by enriching metadata with additional cultural context. This enhances provenance quality and promotes a more equitable approach to data reuse.

"Build TRUST to be FAIR": Hosting HSAs

The TRUST Principles for Digital Repositories—Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability, and Technology—outline the core, long-term capabilities that **trustworthy digital repositories (TDRs)** must provide to enable the access, reuse, and preservation of data, including SAs.¹⁰ They complement the FAIR guidelines by underscoring that long-term preservation is impossible unless a repository delivers these essential services. The FAIRsFAIR project recommends publishing SAs in repositories that are both FAIR and TRUST-compliant,¹¹ such as [re3data](#) and [FAIRsharing](#). By the same token, it cautions against using code-hosting platforms such as GitHub or GitLab for long-term preservation; these services may be suitable

⁹Carroll, S. R., Garba, I., Figueroa-Rodríguez, O. L., Holbrook, J., Lovett, R., Materechera, S., Parsons, M., Raseroka, K., Rodríguez-Lonebear, D., Rowe, R., Sara, R., Walker, J. D., Anderson, J., & Hudson, M. (2020). The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance. *Data Science Journal*, 19, 43. [10.5334/dsj-2020-043](https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043).

¹⁰Lin, D., et al. (2020), «The TRUST Principles for Digital Repositories». *Scientific Data*, 7, 144. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>.

¹¹Best Practice 11 "Use TRUSTed and FAIR compliant repositories to persist Semantic Artefacts" in Hugo, W., Le Franc, Y., Coen, G., Parland-von Essen, J., & Bonino, L. (2020). D2.5 FAIR Semantics Recommendations Second Iteration (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5362010>.

only for short-term archival.

CC Signals: HSAs and AI

We are closely monitoring the **CC Signals** initiative,¹² which aims to establish a standardized framework for articulating preferences regarding the reuse of works in **AI training**. The initiative, primarily targeted at content stewards responsible for large datasets, remains under development, with its launch anticipated in November 2025. While its implications for RADIOSA cannot yet be fully assessed, CC Signals may ultimately shape requirements concerning the attribution and treatment of SAs when subject to machine-mediated reuse.

#2 - Use Semantic Versioning

Versioning is essential for transparency, sustainability, and trust in semantic artefacts (SAs). The ⟨H/RADIOSA⟩ initiative strongly recommends adopting Semantic Versioning (SemVer) as a standard practice.

What Is Semantic Versioning?

Semantic Versioning (SemVer) is a system for numbering software releases so that each version conveys meaningful information.

The format is: MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH.

- MAJOR – incompatible changes (e.g., removal or redefinition of concepts).
- MINOR – backward-compatible additions (e.g., new classes or properties).
- PATCH – backward-compatible fixes (e.g., typos, scope note refinements).

For example:

- 2.3.4 → Major = 2, Minor = 3, Patch = 4

Although originally designed for software, semantic artefacts should also be considered software-like resources, making SemVer highly relevant.

Why It Matters for Heritage Semantic Artefacts

The H-SeTIS survey showed that most heritage semantic artefacts lack structured versioning. This creates problems:

- Users cannot easily track changes over time.
- Breaking changes may disrupt dependent systems without warning.
- Lack of provenance makes it difficult to evaluate trustworthiness.
- How to Implement Versioning

Even when standards such as SKOS or RDFS lack native versioning support, best practices can be applied using widely adopted properties:

- `owl:versionIRI` – persistent identifier for a specific version.
- `owl:versionInfo` – human-readable version number (e.g., SemVer format).
- `owl:priorVersion`, `dcterms:hasVersion` – links between versions.

Git-based repositories (GitHub, GitLab) – to track changes, manage releases, and publish changelogs.

Changelogs and Transparency

Version numbers alone are not enough. Developers should also maintain changelogs, which:

¹² See the report [From Human Content to Machine Data: Introducing CC Signals](#).

- Record all modifications systematically.
- Communicate the scope and impact of changes.
- Help users decide whether to upgrade or adapt.

Changelogs are best managed in open repositories with issue tracking (e.g., GitHub Issues). This allows community members to follow discussions and understand the rationale behind changes.

Practical Example

Change Type	SemVer Level
New classes/properties for new use cases	MAJOR
Deprecation or removal of elements	MAJOR
New single class/property (extends model)	MINOR
Scope note or definition refinement	PATCH
Typos, grammar fixes, small corrections	PATCH

Recommendations

- Always assign **SemVer-style version numbers** to semantic artefacts.
- Use **OWL versioning properties** to embed version information.
- Maintain **public changelogs** in Git repositories.
- Signal **backward-incompatible changes** with a MAJOR version bump.
- Engage with users via issue tracking to document discussions and decisions.

#3 - Set Responsiveness Expectations

Definition

The **responsiveness** status of a semantic artefact reflects its **maintenance level**, its ability to **perform its intended tasks**, and the availability and involvement of its **editors** or **working group**.

List of the Statures

The responsiveness statuses are:

- **Active:** The semantic artefact has a contact person who is responsive. New terms, elements, or features are being added if the semantic artefact is still evolving, or other revisions are made in response to community requests and/or the goals of the editorial team. IRIs are implemented and maintained if needed.
- **Inactive:** The semantic artefact has a responsive contact person, and a current version is available. However, no updates or edits are being made, and requests for changes are either significantly delayed or are not being addressed by the editors.
- **Unresponsive:** The semantic artefact does not have a responsive contact person, but it is still actively maintained. Although updates continue, there is no direct interaction with users or response to external requests.
- **Orphaned:** The semantic artefact was designed and potentially developed to some extent, but it is no longer actively maintained, updated, or supported. The semantic artefact lacks a responsive contact person, and no further edits or updates are being made. Inquiries or requests for edits are not addressed. The semantic artefact is not deprecated or obsolete, but users should be aware that it is effectively discontinued.
- **Obsolete:** The semantic artefact is no longer maintained (either inactive or orphaned), and its original

developers do not recommend its use. This may be because a newer, more suitable resource is available, or previous versions have significant issues or are no longer accessible. Generally, “Obsolete” is a special status that should be assigned by the semantic artefact’s representative, which confirms that the semantic artefact is formally deprecated. This practice is not widespread in the Heritage field.

Usage

One of the aims of the H-SeTIS survey was to assess the responsiveness of existing HSAs. Responsiveness awareness is essential for SAs because it enables them to remain effective within dynamic and heterogeneous ecosystems. It allows artefacts to adapt to evolving knowledge, reflect changes in domain conceptualizations, and sustain interoperability with emerging standards. In doing so, responsiveness preserves the accuracy, reliability, and overall relevance of these artefacts, ensuring they continue to serve as trustworthy knowledge resources.

Beyond technical adaptability, responsiveness also contributes to sustainability and governance. Artefacts designed with mechanisms for refinement and accountability are less prone to obsolescence, foster user confidence, and maintain alignment with community needs. By making modification processes transparent and traceable, responsiveness enhances legitimacy and promotes broader acceptance and adoption across diverse contexts.

To this end, H-SeTIS applies the five labels introduced earlier to indicate the responsiveness status of semantic artefacts. A status is assigned based on **direct communication** with the artefact’s developers, except when sufficient publicly available information allows for an independent determination. If no response is received within two months of contact, the artefact is provisionally labeled Unresponsive or Orphaned; however, labels can be changed at any time after direct contact.

Recommendations

- If you are the author of a semantic artefact **not listed** in the H-SeTIS database, or if you believe an artefact has been **incorrectly labeled**, please **open an issue** to request a new entry or a correction.
- If you are developing or maintaining a semantic artefact, consider **aligning** it with the RADIOSA recommendations to enhance interoperability and long-term sustainability.
- Include all the administrative metadata useful to assess the authorship and responsiveness of HSAs. These comprise `dcterms:author` and `dcterms:contributor` for the former while `dcterms:created`, `dcterms:modified`, `dcterms:license` and `owl:versionIRI` for the latter (as exemplified in section #1 - Be FAIR (Enough)).
- If you believe the current responsiveness statuses need refinement or additional categories, **contribute** suggestions based on real-world cases and your professional expertise.
- **Share** experiences and case studies related to maintaining, updating, or retiring semantic artefacts. Practical examples can help refine and validate the proposed statuses.
- If you work in a Museum, Archive, or other Heritage-related organization, **advocate** for the adoption of these best practices to ensure the longevity and usability of semantic artefacts in the field.
-

#4 - Documentation

Documentation issues

Documentation is another key element when dealing with HSAs. These are the most frequent issues highlighted by the H-SeTIS survey:

- **Lack of consistent documentation.** A primary issue is that documentation for HSAs is often poor or completely absent. If any documentation exists, it is published through academic papers. However, these publications are not a substitute for proper technical documentation, which should provide detailed insights that a scientific paper cannot accommodate. HSAs documentation should be always available online (e.g. without paywalls) in an adequate format. The lack of documentation hinders or even prevents the reuse of these semantic artefacts.
- **Insufficient implementation of embedded documentation.** HSAs rarely provide detailed embedded documentation (*i.e.* embedded metadata), which is crucial for ensuring they are FAIR (Findable,

Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). Embedded metadata, which should be integrated within the artefact itself, is often missing. This includes **licensing information**, as an ambiguous or undeclared license is a significant barrier to reuse, **contact and authorship details**, as information that helps assess an artefact's responsiveness status, such as contact information is often missing, and **community engagement** information, as links to code repositories or issue trackers are seldom included as well.

- **Local and development documentation** is often missing as well. Local documentation stands for metadata used to manage individual components within the artefact, such as documenting changes or improvements to specific classes or properties. Tools like `skos:editorialNote` exist but are not widely used (provide possible solution). This type of documentation is crucial for maintenance and tracking the evolution of the artefact over time. Development documentation means those resources that provide insight into the methodologies used for the development of the HSAs, their update policies, or how author contributions are tracked. This documentation should provide details on the processes behind the creation of the semantic artefact.
- **Failure to distinguish documentation from other outputs.** There is a tendency to merge project deliverables with user documentation. User documentation provides guidelines for implementation and use cases, and it must be regularly updated to remain functional. In contrast, project deliverables are static research outputs and do not fulfill this role.
- **User negligence.** This problem is twofold. Not only is there a lack of sufficient documentation from creators, but users themselves often fail to regularly and carefully consult the existing documentation. This neglect undermines the principle of reusability and hinders the effective, long-term sustainability of a semantic artefact. This issue could have deeper consequences in the Heritage field, considering that many users might not be familiar with IT documentation and the development of SAs, and that subjective interpretations are very frequent.

Proposed Solutions and Best Practices

To address these documentation issues, the ⟨H/RADIOSA⟩ initiative suggests several solutions and best practices, such as **the use standardized frameworks**. When possible, templates like the MIRO (Minimum Information for the Reporting of an Ontology)¹³ guidelines should be adopted to produce consistent and comprehensive documentation. The **Metadata for Ontology Description and Publication Ontology (MOD)**¹⁴ is a metadata vocabulary created to improve the FAIRness of ontologies and other semantic artifacts by making them easier to find, access, reuse, and interoperate with on the Web. It was designed to address the lack of precise ontology metadata, moving beyond general vocabularies like Dublin Core, and to harmonize ontology descriptions across platforms, thereby reducing costs and encouraging reuse.

Since its first release in 2015, MOD has evolved through several versions, most recently MOD 3.2.2, expanding its structure to include dozens of classes and properties for describing semantic artifacts such as taxonomies, terminologies, thesauri, and ontologies in various digital formats. Its development has been guided by a two-pronged methodology that combined high-level conceptual facets with user-driven needs for ontology search and evaluation, while adhering to principles of clarity, simplicity, authority, and interoperability. MOD is deeply aligned with Linked Data practices, ensuring interoperability through extensive reuse of elements from other metadata vocabularies, while addressing the shortcomings of earlier approaches such as OMV. As a DCAT-based extension, it plays a central role in implementing the FAIR principles, particularly by defining minimum metadata schemas and ensuring semantic artifacts and catalogues can be systematically described and shared. Widely adopted in projects like FAIRsFAIR, FAIR-IMPACT, AgroPortal, EcoPortal, and several OntoPortal-based catalogues, MOD has already enhanced interoperability across platforms and continues to serve as a reference standard, with future plans focused on automation, integration with major ontology libraries, and the release of MOD-aligned knowledge bases as Linked Open Data.

An alternative for good embedded metadata documentation is the following metadata set:

¹³ Matentzoglou, N., Malone, J., Mungall, C., & Stevens, R. (2018). MIRO: Guidelines for Minimum Information for the Reporting of an Ontology. *Journal of Biomedical Semantics*, 9(1), 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13326-017-0172-7>

¹⁴ Dutta, B., Nandini, D., & Shahi, G. K. (2015). MOD: Metadata for Ontology Description and Publication. *Proceedings of the 2015 International Conference on Dublin Core and Metadata Applications, DC-2015 in São Paulo, Brazil, 1-4 September 2015*. <https://doi.org/10.23106/DCMI.952136974>

Parameter	Description
<code>dc:terms:title</code>	Title. A human-readable name of the ontology or vocabulary that clearly identifies it.
<code>dc:terms:alternative</code>	Alternative title. Any known abbreviations, acronyms, or alternative names for the ontology to improve discoverability.
<code>dc:terms:author</code>	Author. The main individual(s) or organization(s) responsible for creating the ontology.
<code>dc:terms:contributor</code>	Contributor. Other individuals or organizations that contributed to the development, review, or maintenance of the ontology.
<code>dc:terms:description</code>	Description. A concise summary of the ontology's purpose, scope, and intended use cases, making it easier for others to understand and evaluate its relevance.
<code>dc:terms:created</code>	Date created. The date on which the ontology was originally created, ideally in ISO 8601 format (YYYY-MM-DD).
<code>dc:terms:modified</code>	Date modified. The most recent date the ontology was updated, useful for tracking changes and version management.
<code>dc:terms:license</code>	License. A clear reference (usually via a URI) to the license under which the ontology is distributed, ensuring clarity about reuse rights and restrictions.
<code>dc:terms:bibliographicCitation</code>	Bibliographic citation. The recommended citation to use when referencing the ontology in scholarly or technical works.
<code>vann:preferredNamespacePrefix</code>	Preferred namespace prefix. The short prefix (e.g., foaf, skos) that should be used when referencing ontology terms in RDF or linked data.
<code>vann:preferredNamespaceUri</code>	Preferred namespace URI. The persistent URI that identifies the ontology namespace, ensuring unambiguous reference and linking.
<code>owl:versionIRI</code>	Versioned IRI. The IRI identifying the specific version of the ontology, enabling precise reference to a given release.
<code>pav:version</code>	Version. A human-readable version string (e.g., 1.0, 2.1-beta) that complements the owl:versionIRI.
<code>sw:status</code>	Status. The current maturity or lifecycle status of the ontology (e.g., draft, stable, deprecated), helping users assess reliability and suitability for production use.
<code>foaf:homepage</code>	Homepage. A URL to the project or ontology homepage, providing additional documentation and resources.
<code>foaf:logo</code>	Logo. An image representing the ontology or its project, often useful in portals or catalogues for better recognition.

Acknowledgements

The proposal for the H/RADIOSA initiative has been published in Scarpa, E., Valente, R., Rossi, I. (2025), "H/RADIOSA: Recommended Approaches for the Development of Interoperable Open Semantic Artefacts in the Heritage Domain", in S. Campana, D. Ferdani, H. Graf, G. Guidi, Z. Hegarty, S. Pescarin, and F. Remondino (eds.), Digital Heritage 2025.

H/RADIOSA is an output of the H2IOSC project, WP 4, Activity 4.10, CNR-ISPC - Milan branch.

H2IOSC Project - Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud funded by the European Union NextGenerationEU - National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) - Mission 4 "Education and Research" Component 2 "From research to business" Investment 3.1 "Fund for the realization of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructures" Action 3.1.1 "Creation of new research infrastructures strengthening of existing ones and their networking for Scientific Excellence under Horizon Europe" - Project code IR0000029 - CUP B63C22000730005. Implementing Entity CNR.